

Original Research

Determinants of Tourism Satisfaction in the Cultural and Heritage Sector of Dar es Salaam, Tanzania

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Abstract

This paper presents the findings of a study that assessed the determinants of tourism satisfaction in the cultural and heritage sector of Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. Guided by the Expectation and Confirmation Theory, the study validated the theory in the developing country context of Tanzania in East Africa. The study used a questionnaire survey to collect data from a sample of 100 respondents; however, of these 91 respondents returned the duly filled out self-administered questionnaires. The resultant quantitative data were analysed based on descriptive statistical analysis and inferential statistics. The findings indicate that expectation, confirmation and disconfirmation tourism satisfaction are the determinants of tourism satisfaction in Tanzania's cultural and heritage sector of tourism. Based on the findings, the study recommends that ensuring that tourism-related goods and services consistently meet or exceed visitors' expectations can enable policymakers and other stakeholders to improve confirmation. This will enhance visitor experiences and decrease confirmation by developing the best visitor management strategies. Moreover, the study makes a theoretical contribution by supporting the Expectation Confirmation Theory.

Keywords: Confirmation, disconfirmation, expectation.

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Introduction

Tourism is globally an important part of the socioeconomic development as it fosters economic development and cultural understanding among nations (Kara, 2017). The tourism sector also significantly contributes to economic growth as a premier foreign exchange earner in both developed and developing countries (Burhan et al., 2018) including Tanzania, the focus of this study. Though numerous studies have explored tourism satisfaction in developed countries, little is known about the factors that influence such satisfaction in the context of developing countries (Kara, 2021). Moreover, there is a growing body of literature on tourism satisfaction in developed countries (Tatyana & Dimitar, 2017) relative to the developing nations.

Cultural and heritage tourism is a significant segment within the broader tourism industry, offering as it does unique experiences in addition to promoting the preservation of cultural and historical assets. In the context of Tanzania, cultural and heritage tourism has the potential of contributing significantly to the economy and enhancement of national development (Burhan et al., 2018; WWT, 2021). Despite the availability of improved regulations and policies, many cultural heritage sites in Tanzania remain largely untapped (Bakari, 2021; Kara, 2017). Tanzania, known for its abundant natural and cultural resources, has gained international recognition for its nature-based tourism. The World Economic Forum's Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index ranks Tanzania 1st in Africa and 12th worldwide in terms of nature-based tourism quality (UN Tourism, n.d.). However, the National Tourism Policy of 1999 acknowledges that Tanzania's culture is underdeveloped, there is insufficient community awareness and appreciation of tourism, and there is a lack of investment opportunities and limited community participation in the tourism sector (Luoga, 2017), hence the need for Tanzania to continue re-orienting towards preserving its cultural heritage in addition to enhancing its tourism resources generally. Therefore, it is essential to explore the factors that influence tourism satisfaction specifically in the cultural and heritage tourism sector, as this understanding can contribute to the development and promotion of these sites.

In fact, there is a growing body of literature on cultural and heritage tourism satisfaction in developed countries such as the US America, France, Spain, and Austria and the developing countries of Southern Asia, Southern Europe, and Latin America; yet African countries continue lagging behind (Minh et al., 2023) A World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) study on the economic impact of tourism in 2021 the US, China, Germany, Japan, Italy, South Korea and South Africa found that the economic contribution of tourism to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) was USD 1781 billion USD in the United States, 814,3 USD billion in China, and 206.3 USD billion in Japan. However, the travel and tourism contribution to GDP in Africa in 2021 was USD 119 billion with a generation of 21.3 million jobs whereas in the US the tourism sector employed 34.6 million in the same year. In other words, Africa still lags behind when it comes to how tourism contribute for economic development and, more specifically, for cultural and heritage tourism.

However, in some of the developing countries, the contribution in GDP particularly in South Africa was 13.2 USD billion of the GDP, this findings indicates on the trend on

how tourism contributes less in developing countries, particularly in Africa (WTTC, 2021). For Tanzania, tourism contributed 17.2 percent of its GDP in 2023. Nevertheless, the number of tourists in Tanzania were only 1, 808,205 in 2023 (URT, 2024), which is small number relative to the enormous cultural and heritage products available in the country.

The Expectation Confirmation Theory (ECF) that guided this study accounts for how when individual expectations are fulfilled, they can foster change in attitudes and provide satisfaction (Attapatu et al., 2016). This study, therefore, assessed the factors influencing tourism satisfaction in Tanzania, focusing on the effects of expectation, confirmation and disconfirmation on tourism satisfaction for cultural and heritage sectors in Tanzania. After all, the tourism sector plays a vital role in economic growth and foreign exchange generation of both developed and developing countries (Kyara et al., 2021). Also, customer satisfaction is crucial for the growth of the tourism sector (Asmelash & Kumar, 2019). Indeed, providing better tourism services to clients can lead to satisfaction, which attracts more customers and boosts profitability (Ben Asmelash & Kumar, 2019).

The Tanzania government has made concerted efforts aimed to boost tourism in the country through its diverse policy formulation and strategy implementation; however, the nation's huge cultural and heritage tourism potentials remain largely untapped (Burhan *et al.*, 2018; URT, 2022; WWT, 2021; Kara, 2017). This scenario raises questions regarding what impedes customers' satisfaction in Tanzania, the policies and regulations in place. In fact, there is a paucity of studies on factors influencing tourism satisfaction in Tanzania's cultural and heritage tourism (Ruheza *et al.*, 2016). Theoretically, these disparities call for further research in Tanzania to fill the gap. Thus, this study assessed the factors influencing tourism satisfaction in Tanzania's cultural and heritage tourism. Specifically, the study sought to unveil the effects of expectation, confirmation and disconfirmation in tourism satisfaction for Tanzania's cultural and heritage sectors.

Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Oliver (1980) promulgated the Expectancy Confirmation Theory (ECF), which works on the assumption that when an individual gets expectations fulfilled, change in attitude results, which would lead to satisfaction (Shukla et al., 2023). In this regard, the ECF has four main constructs: expectation, performance, disconfirmation and satisfaction. Expectation is the gap between what a customer anticipates from performance that informs their disconfirmation judgement when dissatisfied, or satisfaction which is deep-rooted in the service meeting or exceeding the customers' expectations. Oliver (1980) argues that the use of products or services for the second time would be influenced by past satisfaction. Notably, disconfirmation has three outputs, which are confirmation that allows actual performances to derive from the anticipated satisfaction, negative disconfirmation that the actual performance does not meet, and the positive disconfirmation whereby the actual performances exceeds the expected performances (Shukla et al., 2023). The Theory holds that people can decide to use the products or services based on past judgement regarding the products or service. When an individual uses these products, then their performances is the pre-requisite of the expectation that becomes the bases of the expectation, which in turn constitutes the satisfaction on the products or services (Shukla et al., 2023)

The numerous theories regarding customers satisfaction, including the Expectancy Confirmation theory notwithstanding, there is no understood variables or factors up to the present that has unveiled the factors that influence satisfaction of customers in tourism industry, specifically on cultural and heritage tourism (Minh et al., 2023). As such, there was a need to undertake this study, which has validated the ECF theory regarding enhancing the novelty of the study (Babbie, 1998). Several studies have emphasised the significance of cultural heritage in attracting tourists in developed countries. However, studies in the context of Tanzania specifically on cultural and heritage in developing countries which are guided by the ECF theory are scant (kara et al., 2021).

Rich cultural traditions, historical sites, and unique customs are instrumental in shaping tourists' perceptions and decisions to visit the country (Kara et al., 2021). However, a gap exists in understanding which specific cultural aspects or historical landmarks have the most significant effect on tourism satisfaction, specifically when it comes to business undertakings in Tanzania, as most of the studies have been conducted in developed countries (Karunanithy & Sivesan, 2013; Monica & Olimpia, 2022; Minh et al., 2023). Some studies have indicated that pre-trip expectations are insignificant in inspiring satisfaction (Boo & Busser, 2018; YE et al., 2019) whereas the post-trip experience has emerged to be significant in accounting for satisfaction (Yoon & Uysal, 2005). In this regard, Monica and Olimpia (2022) assessed the need of tourist destination management for tourist preferences of the place. In Tanzania, Mlozi's (2017) study on the satisfaction as a predictor for loyalty, and Lwoga (2017) focused on community engagement as the component of culture and heritage. However, studies conducted in developed and developing countries have produced mixed results, which give rise to differences in interpretations pertaining to the factors influencing satisfaction in the tourism industry and, more specifically, on cultural and heritage sectors (Minh et al., 2023; Nian et al., 2022).

Beside these mixed results and scanty studies in developing countries particularly in Tanzania, there are scanty specific studies on satisfaction in the context of business undertakings, which prompted this study in an attempt to fill that gap and contribute to the body of knowledge on satisfaction in the hospitality industry. Therefore, the following hypotheses have been developed in undertaking this study:

H₁: Expectations among tourists have a significant influence on the satisfaction in hospitality industry.

H₂: Confirmation among tourists has a significant influence on the satisfaction in hospitality industry.

H₃: Disconfirmation among tourists has a significant influence on the satisfaction in hospitality industry.

Method

Research Design, Population and Approach

This research adopted a deductive approach because the study started with the already developed theories gleaned via literature review before adopting an appropriate the research strategy to test the theories (Kothari & Garg 2014; Saunders et al., 2012). The deductive approach suits a research problem—such as the one espoused in this study—that seeks to explain causal relationships between two or more variables or concepts. Specifically, this study adopted a survey strategy, which helps collect huge amounts of data using questionnaires administered to a study population in a bid to test the hypotheses (Saunders et al 2012) and used a descriptive method to delineate the relationships between variables (Kothari & Garg, 2014)

The study population comprised both local and international tourists at tourism destination specifically those visiting cultural and heritage tourism hubs and consuming products in Dar es Salaam. Dar es salaam has been chosen because are the most conducive and attractive tourist destination in the coastal areas (Africa incoming, 2022). The areas of interest in the sprawling city are the Kariakoo market. Other areas included Karimjee hall, Makumbusho museums, Botanic Gardens located behind Utalii College and artistic artisans based at Mwenge, the city centre and Oysterbay areas. The segmented lifestyles, night life which also included traditional foods, clothes, shops, night clubs, and heritage resources made tourists converge in these areas.

Sampling and Sample Size

The study used a convenience sampling to purposively select the sample. This non-probability sampling is also applicable in quantitative research, especially in situations where practical constraints can limit the selection of participants (Kothari & Garg, 2012).

To determine the sample size, the study adopted Green's (1991) formula, which indicates that, calculating the sample size for multiple regression analysis requires a sample that is greater than $50 + 8m$ by $N > 50 + 8m$, whereby N = sample size and m represents the number of independent variables. Since the study has four independent variables, the required sample size based on the formula was supposed to be 74, but the sample size was greater than 74 as a sample of 100 was drawn from the population and 91 respondents returned the questionnaire.

Measurement

The study used a five-point Likert scale. Using this five-point Likert scale whose values ranged from “strongly disagree” (1) to strongly agree (5), the study measured independent variables—expectation, confirmation and disconfirmation—adapted from (Bhattacharjee et a et al, 2001; Roberts & Grover, 2012a; Roberts & Grover, 2012b) and Tourism satisfaction as dependent variables adapted from Bhattacharjee., et al, 2001).

Ethical Considerations

The researcher followed ethical guidelines throughout the investigation in accordance with Saunders et al.'s (2012) advice, including informing the participants clearly about the purpose and nature of the study. As their participation was voluntary, the study also obtained informed consent from the respondents. Before going to the field, the researcher obtained research clearance that facilitated the conducting of the study. With permission from the director of research, publication, and consulting at the institution, the respondents were reassured of the purpose of data usage and made to feel more comfortable during the data collection process.

Analysis

Respondents' demographic characteristics

The study sample of both domestic and foreign tourists comprised businessperson, who numbered 46 (50.5%) of the respondents and informal sector employees, who amounted to 23 (25.3 %).

Reliability Test results

The study carried out a reliability test was carried out for to assess the variables and determine their internal consistency (Saunders et al., 2012). Moreover, the dependability of the research instruments was assessed using the Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The Cronbach's alpha reliability results yielded a result of 0.939, indicating that the values were over the minimal cut-off point of 0.7. In other words, the questionnaire used to collect data was dependable in assessing the constructs under study (Saunders et al., 2012).

In addition, the study carried out T factor analysis to determine how latent factors explain the observable variables. According to Basto and Pereira (2012), when assessing the sample adequacy of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test for Sphericity (BTS), values larger than 0.6 and a significant value, respectively, indicate that the items qualify for factor analysis. The values of <0.001 and 0.885 in the study's results indicate that the dataset was suitable for factor analysis.

Factor analysis was also conducted to establish how latent factors explain the observable variables. To determine the sample's adequacy, the study applied Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test for Sphericity (BTS). Generally, the cutoff points are value greater than 0.6 and a significant value, respectively, to show that the items are a good-fit for factor analysis (Basto and Pereira, 2012). In this study, the resultant values of <0.001 , and 0.885 that the dataset was appropriate for conducting factor analysis. Also, the study used a cutoff point of above 0.3 on factor loading (Basto and Pereira, 2012). Subsequently, the study retained items with factor loading of above 0.3 for undertaking the factor analysis. Based on the data available, Tourist Satisfaction (TS), Expectation (EX), Confirmation (COF), and Disconfirmation (DIS) were subject ed to factor analysis. The factor loadings, which show the degree of correlation between each variable and its underlying factor, are reported for each variable in these sets.

Furthermore, reports included reliability data such as Cronbach's alpha, the Bartlett's test of sphericity (BTS), and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy.

Table 1. Reliability and Validity of the Data

Reliability Cronbach's alpha	KMO	BTS (P-Value)
0.989	0.885	<0.001

Table 2. Distribution of Factor loadings for TS, EX, CO & DIS

Tourist Satisfaction (TS) variables		Expectation (EX) variables	
Variable	Factor loadings	Variable	Factor loadings
TS7	0.755	EX5	0.761
TS2	0.720	EX6	0.701
TS5	0.677	EX4	0.669
TS6	0.615	EX3	0.656
TS3	0.580	EX2	0.656
TS1	0.568	EX2	0.599
Confirmation (COF) variables			
Variable		Factor loadings	
COF3		0.808	
COF6		0.743	
COF5		0.690	
COF2		0.667	
COF4		0.597	
COF1		0.641	
Disconfirmation (DIS) variables			
Variable		Factor loadings	
DIS2		0.802	
DIS4		0.734	
DIS5		0.715	
DIS1		0.790	
DIS3		0.684	

The Principal Component Analysis is the extraction method used. The Rotation Technique has to do with the Kaiser Normalisation using Varimax. Meanwhile, for every construct, a single component was taken out of the associated variables. There was no rotation of the solution (no rotated component matrix).

Results of Correlation Analysis

According to Senthilnathan (2019), correlation values of between $+0.90$ and 1.00 can indicate a very high connection. High correlation can be found between $+0.70$ and $+0.90$, moderate correlation between $+0.50$ and $+0.70$, low correlation between $+0.30$ and $+0.50$, and little connection between $+0.00$ and $+0.30$. Therefore, when the

correlation (r) is greater than or equivalent to +0.9, multicollinearity in the model is a matter of concern.

Data in Table 3.0 further suggest a causal association between the Tourist satisfaction (TS) and the independent variables, with r correlation ranging from 0.779 to 0.839 at $p < 0.01$. Notably, the research did not reveal any instances of multicollinearity.

Table 3. Inter-Correlation among Variables (N=91)

Correlations		TS	EX	COF	D
Pearson Correlation	TS	1.000	.839	.809	.819
	EX	.839	1.000	.786	.784
	COF	.809	.786	1.000	.779
	D	.819	.784	.779	1.000

**r is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Outcomes

The model fit revealed adjusted R² and R² values of 0.793 and 0.785, respectively, meaning that 79% of the variance in the independent variable can be explained by the dependent variable. The F-statistic was 109.603 at $p < 0.001$. The Durbin-Watson statistic was close to 2. Given that the value displayed was less than 1, there is no indication of any outliers in the data (Daud, 2018).

Table 4. Model Summary & Regression Outputs

R	R squared	Adjusted Squared	The std error of estimate	Dublin Watson	F	Sign (P-value)	
0.795	0.793	0.785	0.552	1.674	109.603	(<0.001)	
Constant	B	Std Error	Beta	t	Sig	Tolerance	VIF
EX	445	.101	.392	4.422	.000	.307	3.253
COF	.289	.098	.260	2.959	.004	.313	3.193
D	.419	.118	.310	3.553	.001	.316	3.162

Influence of Expectation on Tourism Satisfaction

To begin with, the Regression Table 4 depict results at $p=0.000$, which affirm that Expectation is a significant predictor of Tourist Satisfaction. In other words, the results support the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis is accepted and the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Influence of Confirmation on Tourism Satisfaction

Moreover, the Regression Table 4 present results at $p=0.004$, which highlight how confirmation of use is a significant predictor Tourism satisfaction, hence the acceptance of alternative hypothesis and rejection of the null hypothesis.

Influence of Disconfirmation on Tourism Satisfaction

Furthermore, the Regression Table 4 indicates results at $p=0.001$ that Disconfirmation is a significant predictor of Tourism Satisfaction. The result validates the alternative hypothesis and invalidates the null hypothesis.

Discussion

The study results indicate that expectation, confirmation and disconfirmation tourism satisfaction are determinants of tourism satisfaction in Tanzania's cultural and heritage sector of tourism. Tourists develop expectations about their travel experiences based on past experiences, word-of-mouth, advertising, and personal preferences (Minh et al., 2023). These assumptions serve as a standard by which they evaluate real experiences. Given the results, it appears pre-trip expectations have a major impact on how visitors perceive and evaluate their experiences, which is evidenced by the large influence of expectations have on tourism satisfaction. These findings align with previous studies that have indicated pre-trip expectations being significant (Yoon & Uysal, 2005; Monica & Olimpia, 2022; Minh et al.2023; YE et al., 2019), which signalling the necessity and importance of post-trip expectations in enhancing tourist satisfaction.

Moreover, the study findings are consistent with the Expectation Confirmation Theory (ECT), which emphasises expectations as the predictor of satisfaction. In this regard, the results indicate that expectations have a major impact on tourists' satisfaction, an outcome consistent with ECT. This being the case, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternative hypothesis, implying that the initial expectations of tourists are a significant determinant of their satisfaction levels. In line with ECT, the travellers' pre-trip expectations significantly impact on how they perceive and assess their travel experiences (Minh et al.,2023).

Conversely, the study findings are incongruent with the study done by Boo and Busser (2018), and YE et al. (2019) whose studies found that pre-trip expectations to be rather insignificant (Boo & Busser, 2018; YE et al., 2019). The incongruity in the findings might be attributable to contextual factors stemming from variations in geographical factors and types of tourism products found in diverse destinations. Moreover, marketing principles assume that consumers' tastes and preferences for products and services are dynamic and change over time; similarly, the tourists' tastes and preferences change over time (Chille & Shayo, 2021; Kotler,2012)

Additionally, the study found that confirmation occurs when tourists' real experiences match their pre-travel anticipations. Under the ECT, confirmation raises satisfaction levels by reaffirming the initial expectations. Thus, when events live up to expectations, travellers' favourable impressions of their travels are reinforced. In this regard, the validation of confirmation of use as a significant determinant of tourists' satisfaction further supports ECT. In fact, the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis suggests that the match between experiences and their expectations positively impact visitors' satisfaction level. Impliedly, confirmation is important in confirming the travellers' original expectations and raising their level of satisfaction overall, as shown by ECT.

Disconfirmation occurs when visitors' actual experiences diverge from their preconceptions (Shukla et al., 2023). In this regard, the ECT demonstrates that depending on whether the event exceeds or falls short of expectations, disconfirmation can have either positive or negative effects. Whereas negative disconfirmation causes dissatisfaction, positive disconfirmation boosts satisfaction. Consistent with ECT is the observation that disconfirmation strongly predicts tourism pleasure. The adoption of the alternative hypothesis also implies that travellers' satisfaction levels are significantly impacted by differences between their expectations and real experiences. In line with ECT, positive disconfirmation experiences that exceed expectations can increase contentment whereas negative disconfirmation experiences that fall short of expectations can cause dissatisfaction.

Based on the results, the study makes a theoretical contribution by supporting the Expectation Confirmation Theory, which underscores the significance of using expectations, confirmations, and disconfirmations as predictors of tourism satisfaction. In other words, the model developed under this study has shown a high explainable variance in the tourism satisfaction by employing a few variables (Babbie, 1998; Zhou et al., 2017; Venkatesh & Bala, 2008). Future research regarding tourism satisfaction in developed and developing nations might benefit from these findings, which also assess similarities and contrasts and add usefulness to the theoretical and practical components of the Expectation Confirmation Model (Attapatu et al., 2016).

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the study, expectation, confirmation and disconfirmation are important predictors of the tourism satisfaction in Tanzania's cultural and heritage sector of tourism. As such, policymakers can utilise the results pertaining to expectation, confirmation, and disconfirmation in the tourist industry to formulate well-informed policies and strategies capable of bolstering destination competitiveness, elevating visitor contentment, and fostering sustainable tourism development. Moreover, policymakers can utilise these findings to create a favourable tourism environment that benefits both travellers and destination communities by addressing important elements that negatively affect tourists' experiences.

Furthermore, state actors and tourist stakeholders should also work towards improving the policies and strategies to ensure that tourism-related goods and services either meet or surpass visitors' expectations. Policymakers can also put in place quality assurance procedures and standards. In this regard, establishing certification programmes, quality standards, and regulatory frameworks may further enhance the upholding of standards in a variety of tourism-related industries, including lodging, transportation, and tourist attractions. In addition, policymakers and government agencies can improve confirmation experiences and raise satisfaction levels overall by guaranteeing consistent quality.

To improve visitors' experiences and reduce disconfirmation, policymakers and the authorities in Tanzania should create viable visitor management techniques. Place visitor education initiatives, crowd control strategies, and sustainable tourism practices can help manage visitor flows, preserve natural and cultural resources, and uphold a high value visitors' experience. The authorities in Tanzania can also raise satisfaction levels and

encourage destination sustainability by tackling issues such as crowding and environmental deterioration that led to disconfirmation.

The results can also inform initiative aimed to guide destination marketing and promotion initiatives, particularly in tailoring marketing campaigns to communicate effectively destination qualities and experiences by understanding aspects that affect tourists' satisfaction, such as expectation, confirmation, and disconfirmation. Policymakers can also enhance the probability of good confirmation experiences and draw in a happier tourist base by precisely controlling tourists' expectations through genuine and transparent marketing communications.

Areas for Additional Studies

Further research is needed to understand the factors influencing tourists' satisfaction in Tanzania, including perceived preferences, social behavioural characteristics, and behavioural patterns. Such a study could further foster the understanding of Tanzania's historical and cultural tourist sector. As the current study may not accurately reflect factors affecting tourist satisfaction in the community due to its limited scope, future studies should endeavour to use a more varied sample and cover additional regions in different tourist destinations to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the variables affecting tourists' satisfaction and provide valuable information for Tanzanian policymakers, the travel industry, and the business community.

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